

Compression Failure Mechanisms in Foam Core Sandwich

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ABSTRACT: Compression failure mechanisms of sandwich specimens with glass/vinylester face sheets over various PVC foam cores have been examined. Failure modes were identified, and compression strengths were compared to analytical predictions. Short specimens failed by compression failure of the face sheets. At intermediate gage lengths it was found that specimens with a thick low-density core failed in an anti-symmetric face wrinkling mode, while long specimens with thinner core failed by global buckling in the fundamental buckling mode. Predictions of the failure loads were overall in agreement with model predictions.

KEYWORDS: Compression failure, buckling, wrinkling, foam core

INTRODUCTION

A major advantage of composite sandwich structures is that they are stiff, strong and light. The combination of face and core materials of vastly different stiffnesses, however, makes such structures prone to peculiar failure modes, not encountered in homogeneous materials. In the specific and important case of a sandwich loaded in compression there are several possible modes of failure, see Fig. 1. The load at which a sandwich structure fails depends on the properties of the face and core materials, on the geometry of the structure and the loading conditions [1]. One possibility is that the face sheets fail in compression, Fig. 1a. Sandwich structures with thin face sheets and soft lightweight cores, however, may be prone to a type of local instability failure called face wrinkling [2-5], Fig. 1b, where the face sheets buckle in a wavelength of the same order as the thickness of the core. Since sandwich structures typically exhibit little or no post-wrinkling load carrying capability, failure by wrinkling is typically catastrophic [2-5]. Longer, unsupported specimens tend to fail in a global buckling mode, Fig. 1c. If the deformation continues to be imposed after buckling, shear crimping [1], Fig. 1d, which involves shear cracking of the core, may occur.

In this study we will examine the compressive failure of sandwich specimens consisting of glass/vinylester composite face sheets over various cross-linked PVC foams. A compression test fixture was designed based on the ASTM C 364 standard enabling compression testing of unsupported sandwich specimen over a range of gage lengths. Failure modes are examined and ultimate loads are compared to predictions from analytical expressions.

Figure 1 Failure modes of compression loaded sandwich specimens: (a) Failure due to compression failure of face sheet, (b) face wrinkling, (c) global buckling, and (d) shear crimping.

REVIEW OF FAILURE ANALYSES

The mechanics associated with the failure modes illustrated in Fig. 1 and analyses for prediction of the ultimate load are reviewed. The analysis and experiments described herein all refers to symmetric sandwich specimens, i.e., sandwich specimens with identical face sheets. Unsymmetrical sandwich specimens tend to introduce loading eccentricities, which complicate the analysis of the compressive response.

Failure due to compression failure of the face sheets, illustrated in Fig. 1a, occurs when the maximum stress in the face sheets reaches its ultimate value. Such failures tend to occur by micro-buckling of the fibers inside the composite [6]. Because the face sheets are much stiffer than the foam core, the compressive load carried by the core is neglected. Based on this assumption, the compression failure load of the sandwich is given by,

$$P_{fail} = 2X_F^C b t_F \quad (1)$$

where X_F^C is the compressive strength of the faces, b the width and t_F is the thicknesses of the faces, see Fig. 2.

Figure 2 Definition of cross-sectional parameters for a sandwich specimen.

Wrinkling is a local buckling instability associated with short waves of the faces resulting from lack of lateral support from the core, Fig. 1b. Wrinkling may occur in symmetrical and anti-symmetrical modes as illustrated in Fig. 3 [2].

Figure 3 Face wrinkling modes. a) symmetrical, and b) anti-symmetrical.

According to the analysis presented by Hoff and Mautner [3], symmetrical wrinkling occurs in sandwich specimens having a core-to-face sheet thickness ratio (t_c/t_f) is greater than 18, and by anti-symmetric wrinkling if the ratio is less than 18. Once the face sheets wrinkle, they tend to lose further load-carrying ability, and fail at a weak location. Figure 4 shows a detailed picture of the localized deformation associated with the wrinkling failure. The core is affected by the deformation of the face sheet in a zone of depth h , and length l .

Figure 4 Shape of a wrinkle.

Global buckling is a failure mode that may occur at long unsupported gage lengths, Fig. 1c. The critical buckling load per unit width of the sandwich is given by [5]:

$$\frac{1}{P_{cr}} = \frac{1}{P_b} + \frac{1}{P_s} \quad (2)$$

where P_b and P_s are the buckling loads per unit width in pure bending and transverse shear respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sandwich panels consisting of glass/vinylester laminate faces over various cross-linked PVC foam cores were examined. One sandwich panel consisted of 3.6 mm thick E-glass/vinylester faces over a 50 mm thick H100 PVC foam core (KTH), another consisted of 3.6 mm thick E-glass/vinylester face sheets over a 50 mm thick H200 PVC foam core (KKV) and three panels consisting of 2 mm thick S-glass/vinylester face sheets with 50, 12.5 and 50 mm thick H45, R75, and H100 PVC foam cores, respectively (TU). The top and bottom face sheets were in all cases manufactured using vacuum-assisted resin injection molding (VARIM) directly on the foam core. The resin was cured at room temperature. Details of the specimens and processing are presented in Refs. [7,8]. Thicknesses defined in Fig. 2, and mechanical property data for the face and core materials are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 Thicknesses and Mechanical Properties of the Face and Core Materials.

Face sheet	Core	t_F mm	t_C mm	E_F GPa	X_F^C MPa	E_C MPa	G_C MPa
Glass/vinylester (KTH)	H100	3.6	50	21.3 ± 0.3	365 ± 5	111	40
Glass/vinylester (KKV)	H 200	3.6	50	23.2 ± 0.2 (x) 11.6 ± 0.6 (y)	405 ± 72 (x) 180 ± 6 (y)	165	90
Glass/vinylester (TU)	H 45	2.0	50	20.6 ± 0.3	177 ± 3	42	18
Glass/vinylester (TU)	R 75	2.0	12.5	20.6 ± 0.3	177 ± 3	56	26 ± 0.5
Glass/vinylester (TU)	H 100	2.0	50	20.6 ± 0.3	177 ± 3	105	40

Symbols E, X and G represent elastic modulus, strength and shear modulus respectively. Superscript C represents compression, and subscripts F and C represent face and core.

An end-loading compression test fixture based on the ASTM C364-99 standard [13], Fig. 5, was used to measure the compressive load-strain response of the sandwich specimens. As the sandwich specimen is end loaded, it is important that the fixture and ends of the sandwich are properly aligned and parallel. Rectangular steel clamps are used to position the specimen at the center of the fixture and to clamp the sandwich specimen. The length of the clamped region was 25.4 mm. The load is applied to the ends of the sandwich faces through platens attached to the crosshead and base of the test machine. For several specimens, both sides were strain gaged to monitor the axial response during loading. All specimens were nominally 37.5 mm wide.

Figure 5 Sandwich compression end-loading test fixture.

The tests were conducted in x direction for KTH sandwich, and x and y directions for the KKV sandwich. Note that the properties in the x and y directions of the TU sandwich should coincide due to the balanced weave and lay-up used. Hence only one direction was examined. Two replicate KTH specimens with gage lengths of 25, 50 and 75 mm were tested. Two replicate KKV sandwich specimens were tested at gage lengths ranging from 25 to 125 mm in increments of 25 mm. Two or three TU replicate specimens with H45 and H100 foam cores were tested at gage lengths ranging from 25 to 150 mm in increments of 25 mm. Two replicate specimens of the TU sandwich with R 75 foam core were tested at gage lengths of 25, 50, 75, 100, 125, 150, 175, 200 and 250 mm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 6a shows a photograph of a failed KTH sandwich specimen with a gage length of 25 mm. The specimen failed due to compression failure of the face sheets at a load of 80 kN. The load - strain response curve, Fig. 6b, shows that both sides display practically identical strains up to failure, which occurred at strain of approximately 1.4%. This is an indication of proper loading and compression failure of the face sheets.

Figure 6 Compression failure of a KTH specimen at 25 mm gage length. a) photograph of failed sandwich as a result of face sheet compression failure, b) load-strain response.

(a)

(b)

The KTH specimens with a gage length of 50 mm similarly failed due to compression failure of the face sheets. At a gage length of 75 mm, however, the KTH specimens failed by wrinkling, Fig. 7a, in an anti-symmetric mode (Fig. 3b). As shown in Fig. 7b, the load-strain response bifurcates at onset of wrinkling.

Figure 7 Compression failure of a KTH specimen at 75 mm gage length. a) photograph of the wrinkling failure, b) load-strain response indicating bifurcation.

(a)

(b)

The KKV specimens were tested over a range of gage lengths in both principal directions. All specimens failed due to compression failure of face sheets. Table 2 lists compression test results for the KKV sandwich.

Table 2 Ultimate Loads and Strains for KKV Sandwich

Gage length, mm	P _{ult} kN		ε _{ult} , %	
	x	y	x	y
25	100	53	1.40	1.72
50	105	51	1.52	1.71
75	88.5	50	1.43	1.51
100	102	48	1.50	1.41
125	91.2	49	1.44	1.32

The failure loads and ultimate strains show consistency over the range of gage lengths examined as a result of single failure mechanism, i.e., face sheet compression failure.

TU specimens with 50 mm thick H 45 core were tested over a range of gage lengths from 25 to 150 mm. All specimens failed due to compression failure of face sheet. Table 3 summarizes the compression test results for the TU sandwich specimens with H45 core.

Table 3 Ultimate Loads for TU Sandwich with H45 core

Gage length, mm	Load, kN
25	21.4± 0.5
50	21.3 ± 0.3
75	21.5 ± 0.2
100	20.0 ± 0.5
125	20.9 ± 0.1
150	20.1 ± 0.5

Consistency in the failure loads is observed over the range of gage lengths examined.

The TU specimens with a 12.5 mm thick R 75 core were tested over a range of gage lengths from 25 to 250 mm. The 25 mm gage length specimen failed by face sheet compression at a load of 22 kN (in average). At longer gage lengths, each specimen failed in a global buckling mode as shown in Fig. 8a. The buckling failure of the specimens was manifested by a bifurcation of the load vs. strain response, Fig. 8b, followed by a load decrease.

Figure 8 Compression (buckling) failure of a TU specimen at 150 mm gage length. a) photograph of buckling shape, b) load-strain response indicating bifurcation.

(a)

(b)

Table 4 summarizes the compression test results and the failure modes for the TU sandwich specimens with R75 core.

Table 4 Ultimate Loads and Failure Modes of TU Sandwich with R75 core

Gage length, mm	Load, kN	Failure Mode
25	22.0± 0.5	Face compression
50	16.4 ± 0.3	Global buckling
75	15.1 ± 0.2	Global buckling
100	13.8 ± 0.3	Global buckling
125	15.4 ± 0.1	Global buckling
150	12.3 ± 0.5	Global buckling
175	10.8 ± 0.3	Global buckling
200	8.8 ± 0.1	Global buckling
250	10.3 ± 0.4	Global buckling

There is a trend of decreasing ultimate load with increasing gage length, consistent with buckling failure. All the specimens, except the one with a 25 mm gage length, failed in a global buckling mode.

TU specimens with 50 mm thick H 100 core were tested over a range of gage lengths from 25 to 150 mm. All specimens failed due to compression failure of face sheet. Table 5 summarizes the compression test results for the TU sandwich specimens with H100 core.

Table 5 Ultimate Loads for TU Sandwich with H100 core

Gage length, mm	Load, kN
25	23.2± 0.2
50	25.6 ± 0.5
75	23.7 ± 0.2
100	26.0 ± 0.1
125	26.5 ± 0.2
150	22.0 ± 0.5

MODEL PREDICTIONS

Axial stiffness and compression failure loads of the sandwich specimens examined are compared to analytical predictions. Table 6 lists the axial stiffness ($\Delta P/\Delta \epsilon$) for the KTH and KKV specimens obtained from experiment and analysis, based on face sheet moduli listed in Table 1. The experimentally measured stiffnesses are in good agreement with the predictions. For the TU sandwich specimens, the axial stiffness was not evaluated from the test results because the specimens were not strain gaged.

Table 6 Measured and Predicted Axial Stiffnesses of KTH and KKV Specimens

Sandwich	Stiffness, MN/m	
	Experimental	Prediction
KTH	153 ± 0.7	167
KKV	178 ± 0.3 (x)	167 (x)
	87.5 ± 0.8 (y)	83.5 (y)

The KTH specimens were found to fail due to face sheet compression failure at 25 and 50 mm gage lengths. Prediction of the ultimate load at these gage lengths is based on Eq. (1). Wrinkling failure of the KTH specimen requires a gage length longer than the half wavelength, l , shown in Fig. 4. The core-to-face thickness ratio for this sandwich is 14, which, according to the Hoff and Mautner [2] analysis, would indicate that the sandwich wrinkles in the anti-symmetric mode shown in Fig. 3b. This was indeed observed, see Fig. 7a. The affected zone in the core, h , Fig. 4, calculated from Ref. [3] for anti-symmetrical wrinkling is 63.3 mm. Since $2h$ exceeds the core thickness (50 mm) the wrinkling induces deformations inside the entire core. The predicted wrinkling load and half wavelength based on “thin core” and antisymmetric wrinkling [3] are $P_w = 122$ kN, $l = 43$ mm. The experimental wrinkling load is evaluated from the load-strain response shown in e.g. Fig. 7b as the load at which the responses from the two strain gages bifurcate. Table 7 summarizes measured and predicted failure loads and wrinkling wavelengths for the KTH sandwich.

Table 7 Measured and Predicted Failure Loads and Wrinkling Wavelengths for the KTH Sandwich

Gage Length mm	Failure Mode	Failure Load, kN		Half Wavelength mm	
		Exp.	Pred.	Exp.	Pred.
25, 50	Face compression	80 ± 2.0	112	N/A	N/A
75	Face wrinkling	79 ± 3.0	122	38 ± 0.5	43

The failure load prediction based on face compression failure exceeds the measured values. The reason for the lower than predicted measured failure load may be attributed to the end-loading configuration of the test fixture. Inspection of failed specimens revealed end failures. Also the wrinkling failure load prediction exceeds the measured value. Over-prediction of the wrinkling load was already noted by Hoff and Mautner [3] who recommended the following design formula as a conservative estimate of the wrinkling load,

$$P_w = bt_F \sqrt[3]{E_F E_C G_C} \quad (6)$$

Application of this formula yields the following wrinkling load for the KTH sandwich, $P_w = 63.3$ kN, which indeed is a conservative approximation to the measured failure load, Table 7.

The KKV specimens with a 50 mm thick H200 core failed due to face sheet compression failure in both x and y directions. Table 8 lists the measured and predicted (Eq. (1)) failure loads for the KKV sandwich.

Table 8 Measured and Predicted Failure Loads for the KKV Sandwich

Gage Length mm	Direction	Failure Load, kN	
		Experimental	Prediction
25, 50, 75, 100 and 125	<i>x</i>	97.5±0	110
25, 50, 75, 100 and 125	<i>y</i>	50.2±0	51

The KKV specimens failed in the gage section, away from the loaded ends, which may explain the good agreement observed in Table 8.

Next we will examine the TU specimen with a 12.7 mm R75 core. The shortest TU specimen tested, with a gage length of 25 mm, failed in face sheet compression failure mode at a load of 22 ± 1.2 kN. This value is consistent with the predicted failure load of 25 kN (Eq. (1)). The TU sandwich specimens with a 12.7 mm thick R75 core tested at gage lengths ranging from 50 to 250 mm failed in a global buckling mode. Figure 11 shows measured and predicted (based on Eq. (5)) critical loads for the TU sandwich specimens. Although there is a substantial scatter, the prediction is consistent with the experimental trend.

Figure 11 Measured and predicted failure loads for TU sandwich.

The TU specimens with 50 mm thick H45 and H100 foam cores failed due to face sheet compression failure. Table 9 lists measured averages and predicted (Eq. (1)) failure loads for the TU sandwich specimens with H45 and H100 foam cores. The prediction is in good agreement with the experimental results for the sandwich specimens with the stiffer core H100. The lesser strength of the H45 sandwich specimens may be due to its softer core, Table 1, providing less lateral support to the face sheets. It should be mentioned that the Hoff-Mautner formula, Eq. (6), predicts wrinkling failure at loads of 34 kN and 60 kN for the TU specimens with H45 and H100 cores, respectively, i.e. much larger than the failure loads observed due to face sheet compression.

Table 9 Measured and Predicted Failure Loads for TU Sandwich

Core	Gage Length, mm	Failure Load, kN	
		Experimental	Prediction
H45	25, 50, 75, 100, 125and 150	21.3±0.4	26.3
H100	25, 50, 75, 100, 125and 150	24.8±0.8	26.3

CONCLUSIONS

The experimental study on compression failure of foam core sandwich specimens with composite face sheets revealed failure modes ranging from face sheet compression to global buckling depending on core stiffness, core thickness and gage length. By varying the gage length from short to long it was found that the failure mode shifted from face sheet compression to wrinkling, while even longer specimens failed by global buckling. Predictions of failure loads for face compression and global buckling were found to be overall consistent with experimental data. It was found that the classical Hoff - Mautner design formula provided conservative results for the wrinkling load.

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